

Psychological Well-Being among Patients with Lower Urinary Tract Syndrome in Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia

Nor Asyikin Fadzil¹⁾, Sejeeetra Raynee Tanapalla¹⁾, Zahiruddin Othman¹⁾,
Wan Mokhzani Mokhter²⁾

ABSTRACT

Background: Lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) in benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) negatively impact the psychological well-being of patients and may relate to the emergence of anxiety and depression.

Objective: The present study aimed to investigate the prevalence of anxiety and depression among patients with LUTS/BPH as well as to determine their correlations.

Method: A cross-sectional study was conducted from July to October 2019 on 153 LUTS/BPH patients under surgical outpatient follow-ups at Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM). A set of self-administered questionnaires comprising the sociodemographic profile, International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS), and Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) were used. Data were analysed using measures of frequency for the prevalence of anxiety and depression in LUTS/BPH and correlation analysis to study the relationship between them.

Result: The study reported the prevalence of depression and anxiety at 27.5% and 15.0% respectively among patients with LUTS/BPH. There was positive correlation between severity of depression ($r = 0.426$, p -value < 0.001) and anxiety ($r = 0.367$, p -value < 0.001) with severity of LUTS/BPH.

Conclusion: Depression and anxiety are prevalence among patients with LUTS/BPH in Hospital USM. There is also a positive correlation between the severity of depression and anxiety with severity of LUTS/BPH. Comorbidity of these conditions should draw the attention of both psychiatrists and urologists as well as enhance interdisciplinary treatment approach to improve the patient's psychological well-being.

KEY WORDS

lower urinary tract syndrome, benign prostatic hyperplasia, anxiety, depression, psychological well-being

INTRODUCTION

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is highly prevalent in ageing men and commonly presents with bothersome lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS), which can be obstructive symptoms such as hesitancy, incomplete voiding, post-void dribbling, or irritative symptoms such as urgency, frequency, and nocturia¹⁾. The prevalence of pathological benign prostatic hyperplasia is only 8% in the fourth decade; however, it increases to 50% when they are 51 to 60 years old²⁾. Although LUTS and BPH (LUTS/BPH) are not considered life-threatening conditions, studies have demonstrated a diverse array of adverse impacts on personal and public health, including mental health as well as health-related quality of life³⁾.

A study conducted in Singapore revealed that there was a high prevalence of anxiety (10.3%) and depression (21.6%) among patients with benign prostatic hyperplasia⁴⁾. Additionally, a prevailing trend toward anxiety and depression was also observed in almost 30% of the other LUTS subgroup populations⁵⁾.

For many years, the directional relationship between the occurrence of LUTS/BPH with depressive and neurotic symptoms has been observed. Therefore, the severity of one condition would most likely affect the severity of the other condition as well. The LUTS/BPH symptoms were more severe in patients with depression, and anxious patients

showed numerically higher LUTS/BPH symptoms than non-anxious patients³⁾. In elderly men, moderate to severe LUTS/BPH is significantly associated with an increased risk of having clinically relevant depressive symptoms⁷⁾. Compared with non depressed patients, depressed patients had more severe LUTS⁸⁾ with ultimately having a three fold increased risk of presenting with severe LUTS⁹⁾.

The current practice of managing benign prostatic hyperplasia focuses on relieving physical symptoms. Besides, the impact of benign prostatic hyperplasia on the patients' health-related quality of life and psychological wellbeing remains understudied, especially in the Asian population⁴⁾. Thus, this study aims to determine the prevalence of depression and anxiety among patients with LUTS/BPH on medication in HUSM and assess the correlation between the severity of LUTS/BPH with the severity of depressive and anxiety symptoms.

METHODS

Characteristics of the study participants

Totally 153 persons agreed to participate in the study. The mean age

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1) Department of Psychiatry, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia
Kubang Kerian, Malaysia

2) Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia
Kubang Kerian, Malaysia.

Correspondence to: Nor Asyikin Fadzil
(e-mail: drasyikin@usm.my)

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants

Variables	Number of participants; n (%)
Number of respondents	153 (100)
Mean age (SD)	68.97 (8.24)
Race	
Malays	136 (88.9)
Non-Malays	17 (11.1)
Marital status	
Married	150 (98.0)
Divorced	3 (2.0)
Single	0 (0)
Education level	
Primary	43 (28.1)
Secondary	70 (45.8)
Tertiary	33 (21.6)
Uneducated	7 (4.6)
Employment status	
Employed	15 (9.8)
Part-time employment	12 (7.8)
Unemployed/retired	126 (82.4)
Total family income (MYR per month)	
< 1000	45 (29.4)
1000-RM2000	58 (37.9)
2001-RM3000	25 (16.3)
3001-RM4000	13 (8.5)
4001-RM5000	5 (3.3)
> 5000	7 (4.6)
Presence of caretaker	
Yes	117 (76.5)
No	36 (23.5)
Co-morbid medical illness	
Yes	87 (56.9)
No	66 (43.1)

of the participants was 68.97 (SD 8.24) years, and most of the participants were Malays (88.9%). Most of the participants received education up to secondary (45.8%) and primary level (28.1%). Only 15 participants (9.8%) were still working, 12 (7.8%) have part-time employment whilst the rest were unemployed or retired. Most of the patients were married (98.0%). Besides that, 117 participants (76.5%) have a caretaker. Slightly above half of the total number of participants (56.9%) have a co-morbid medical illness. (Table 1)

Study Designs and Procedures

Ethical approval was obtained from the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM/JEPeM/18120780). This cross-sectional study was conducted at the surgical outpatient clinic, Hospital USM between July to October 2019. A sample size of 153 participants was calculated by using Power and Sample Size Program software. The participants were diagnosed with LUTS/BPH by clinical and laboratory assessment for at least 6 months duration, receiving pharmacological treatment for LUTS/BPH, and never underwent any surgical intervention for prostate-related condition. Patients with severe cognitive impairment or severe mental illness were excluded from the study. The participants were informed of the purpose of the study before obtaining written consent. They were assured of the confidentiality of their identity and personal data, and their rights to withdraw from the study at any time.

Measures

Socio-demographic Questionnaire

Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants in this study included basic demographics such as age, race, marital status, employment status, total family income, educational level, as well as clinical information such as duration of illness, history of psychiatric illness, medical co-morbidities, and history of prostate-related surgeries.

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS)

The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) is a self-administered questionnaire specifically designed for screening anxiety and depressive symptoms. The 14-item scale consists of two subscales corresponding to Depression (HADS-D) and Anxiety (HADS-A). The items are scored from 0 to 3 (four-point Likert scales), giving maximum scores of 21 for anxiety and depression respectively. Scores were categorized as normal (0–7), mild (8–10), moderate (11–14), and severe (15–21)¹⁰. The translated and validated scale in Bahasa Malaysia was used¹¹. The internal consistency of the scale is excellent, with Cronbach's alpha of 0.88 for the anxiety subscale and 0.79 for the depression subscale. Test-retest Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) is 0.35 and 0.42 for Anxiety and Depression Subscale, respectively. Small mean differences were observed at test-retest measurement with an ESI of 0.21 for anxiety and 0.19 for depression¹².

International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS)

The International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) is a self-administered questionnaire with a reproducible scoring system. It can be utilized used to measure the severity of LUTS in BPH and the response to therapy. The translated and validated scale in Bahasa Malaysia was used. A high degree of internal consistency was observed for each of the 7 items and the total score (Cronbach's alpha 0.53 and greater, and 0.68, respectively). The test-retest correlation coefficients of the 7 items were highly significant. The intraclass correlation coefficient was high at 0.51 and greater.¹³ The scale contains seven questions related to voiding symptoms and one question related to the patient's perceived quality of life. The symptom subscales are scored from 0 to 5 (six-point Likert scales). A score of 0 to 7 indicates mild symptoms, 8 to 19 indicates moderate symptoms and 20 to 35 indicates severe symptoms.

Statistical Analysis

The data entry and analysis were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Study (SPSS) Version 24. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the socio-demographic characteristics of subjects. Age was expressed in mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Categorical data were presented as frequency (percentage). All data were analyzed to ascertain the normality of the distribution. The dependent variables in this study were the scoring of IPSS and HADS. Pearson's product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship between anxiety and depression with LUTS/BPH. A p-value of less than 0.05 was taken as a statistically significant result.

RESULTS

Severity of LUTS/BPH among patients with LUTS/BPH

The level of severity for LUTS/BPH among the participants scored by IPSS was 19% mild, 62.7% moderate and 18.3% severe. (Figure 1)

Severity of depression and anxiety among the participants with LUTS/BPH

Based on the cut-off point of 8 and above, 27.5% of patients had depression with 10.5% in mild, 11.8% in moderate, and 5.2% in severe categories respectively. Also, 15.0% of patients have anxiety with 8.5% in mild, 5.2% in moderate, and 1.3% in severe categories respectively

Figure 1: Severity of lower urinary tract syndrome/ benign prostatic hyperplasia among the participants

Figure 2: Severity of depression and anxiety among the participants with lower urinary tract syndrome/benign prostatic hypertrophy

(Figure 2).

Relationship of LUTS/BPH with anxiety and depression

The mean result IPSS was 12.93 (SD 6.39), while the mean score for HADS-A was 4.68 (SD 3.46) and HADS-D was 5.72 (SD 4.37).

Pearson's correlation coefficients measured the linear relationship between the severity of LUTS/BPH with the severity of anxiety and depression. There was a significant and moderate positive correlation between HADS-D and IPSS ($r = 0.426$, p -value < 0.001) as well as a significant with slight positive correlation for HADS-A and IPSS ($r = 0.367$, p -value < 0.001). (Table 2)

DISCUSSION

This study explored the prevalence of depression and anxiety among patients with lower urinary tract syndrome (LUTS) in benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) on medication in Hospital USM, Malaysia as well as the correlation between the severity of those conditions.

The prevalence of depression was 27.5% among the participants in this study. This finding is in line with the report released by the National Health Morbidity Survey (NHMS) that the prevalence of depression among adults of 16 years and above in Malaysia showed an increasing trend, escalating from 10.7% in 1996 to 29.2% in 2015¹⁴. Moreover, this data is consistent with the findings of a cohort study conducted in Georgia, whereby 22% of patients with benign prostatic hyperplasia were screened positive for depressive symptoms¹⁵.

The prevalence of anxiety in this study was 15.0% which closely corresponded to the findings of a local study that reported that the prevalence of anxiety among adults in the general community was 8.2% and approximately 13% among adults with chronic diseases¹⁶. As benign prostatic hyperplasia is known to be a chronic illness; this finding is consistent with findings from previous studies. On the contrary, another

observational study reported a higher level of anxiety with 35.9% of men with LUTS who met the criteria for clinical anxiety (HADS-A)¹⁷. However, this study included patients from non-specific etiologies of LUTS which could be secondary to a more severe and chronic in origin, hence leading to a higher prevalence of anxiety among them.

The association between LUTS with anxiety and depression could be attributable to several different mechanisms. LUTS reduce health-related quality of life that can lead to embarrassment, social anxiety, demoralization, and poor self-esteem¹⁸. Moreover, having LUTS may be perceived by the patients themselves, as well as their partners and family as a sign of weakness and ageing¹⁹. Furthermore, nocturia and disturbed sleep both result in daytime drowsiness, inability to concentrate, and subsequent anxiety⁸. Consequent to this significant LUTS-related emotional distress, affective disorders may develop²⁰.

Also, it has been suggested that stress accompanied by anxiety and/or depression may be an important factor contributing to the development and prolongation of LUTS²¹. Moreover, some antidepressants and anxiolytics have been suggested as the risk factors for LUTS²².

Frequently used medications to treat LUTS secondary to BPH such as 5- α -reductase inhibitors (5-ARIs; eg, finasteride and dutasteride) and α -adrenergic antagonists (α -blockers; eg, prazosin, terazosin, doxazosin, and alfuzosin)²³ may cause side effects such as incontinence and erectile dysfunction which can lead to anxiety/depression²⁴.

Other possible mechanisms explaining the coexistence of LUTS with depression and anxiety involve an altered concentration of serotonin and norepinephrine in the central nervous system in patients with LUTS, as well as, in those with anxiety and depression²⁵. It is possibly contributing to the development of clinical symptoms and even treatment outcomes in patients with LUTS secondary to BPH²⁶.

Furthermore, increased adrenergic tone and the hypothalamic-pituitary axis have been proposed to mediate depressive symptoms and LUTS²⁴. Finally, it is well known that inflammation contributes to the pathophysiology of major depression; depressed patients often exhibit significant increases in inflammatory biomarkers such as C-reactive protein, interleukin-6, and tumour necrosis factor- α ²⁷.

The second outcome measured in this study was the correlation between the severity of depression and anxiety with the severity of LUTS/BPH. In this study, the sum of points obtained in the IPSS scale was positively correlated with the score on the depression subscale ($r = 0.426$; $p < 0.001$) which is closely comparable to a Polish study ($r = 0.43$; $p < 0.05$)²⁸.

In a cross-sectional, population-based study, men reporting moderate to severe depression had higher odds of reporting LUTS. Besides, more severe LUTS were associated with significantly higher odds of moderate to severe depression and higher odds of suicidal ideation¹⁸.

The results of the study indicate the need for an interdisciplinary approach for patients suffering from depression and experiencing LUTS as they often co-exist and influence each other's severity due to the bi-directional nature of the relationship. This justifies the use of the IPSS questionnaire by psychiatrists as a screening tool to assess the severity of LUTS in patients suffering from depressive disorders as well as the use of self-assessment scales by urologists for cases of suspected depression in patients treated for LUTS to improve the situation of patients.

The sum of points obtained in the IPSS scale in this study was also positively correlated with the score on the anxiety subscale ($r = 0.367$; $p < 0.001$). It is a weak correlation but proven to be significant. This is comparable with the result from the previous study which also demonstrated a positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) that concluded anxiety level (HADS-A) increased with higher LUTS (AUASI)²⁹. A Taiwanese cohort study reported that LUTS patients were 2.12 (95% CI: 1.95–2.30) times more likely to develop anxiety and patients with anxiety were 2.01 (95% CI: 1.88–2.14) times more likely to develop LUTS³⁰.

Unresolved LUTS and bothersome symptoms caused by LUTS increased the trait anxiety in patients on pharmacological treatment as most of the patients on α blockers complained of little improvement in their LUTS. On the contrary, patients with surgical treatment experienced a great reduction in their anxiety level, largely due to the improvement of LUTS, which in turn improved their quality of life³¹. Therefore this strongly suggests that severe LUTS contributes to a higher level of anxiety that may benefit early intervention by the psychological approach.

The main strength of this study is the first study done in Malaysia which focused on the correlation between the severity of LUTS/BPH with the severity of anxiety and depression that covers the large gap in emphasizes the important relationship between LUTS/BPH and depression to developed therapeutic strategies. However, the limitations in this study were the cross-sectional study design, the heterogeneity of phar-

Table 2: The relationship between lower urinary tract syndrome with anxiety and depression.

	Lower urinary tract syndrome (IPSS)	
	R	p-value
Anxiety (HADS-A)	0.367*	< 0.001
Depression (HADS-D)	0.426*	< 0.001

*Pearson correlation

macotherapy among the participants, the lack of a control group and using a self-rated questionnaire. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a prospective multicentre type of study to confirm the relationships observed in this paper.

CONCLUSION

This study adds to the existing evidence that men with severe LUTS/BPH have a higher risk of depression and anxiety than do those with mild and moderate LUTS/BPH. It also emphasizes the important relationship between LUTS/BPH and depression. It offers an insight into the relevance of clinically moderate and severe symptoms of prostatic disease and showed that an association with anxiety/depression exists in all stages of LUTS/BPH. It is, therefore, necessary to conduct further, cohort or prospective, multicenter studies to finally confirm the relationships observed in this paper as well as to help identify patients at risk and develop novel therapeutic strategies.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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